

Monocular vision for pose estimation in space based on cone projection

Jiangping Mei, Dian Zhang, Yabin Ding*

Tianjin University, Key Laboratory of Mechanism Theory and Equipment Design, Ministry of Education, No.135 Yaguan Road of Haihe Education Park, Tianjin, PR China, 300350

Abstract. This paper presents a 3D pose estimation algorithm based on monocular vision. The algorithm relies on the circle target whose radius is known, with the scale condition given, the depth information of the circle can be recovered incompletely, and finally the pose of the target can be estimated by single projection only. Firstly, the circle target has been mapped to be an upright elliptic cone in the pinhole imaging model. Secondly, radius constraint has been applied to recover part depth of the circle target based on the upright elliptic cone. Experimental work concerning the validity and accuracy of this method is presented, furthermore, a application case for robot aided-positioning have been introduced.

Keywords: circle projection, 3D pose estimation, cone geometry, parallel robot positioning.

*Yabin Ding, E-mail: tjurobot@sina.com

1 Introduction

Industrial robot has been widely used in automated factory to improve the working efficiency and reduce labor cost. Aided-positioning technique, which measures the real-time relative pose between object and robot by sensors or instruments, make it possible for robot to acquire the pose of object adaptively, overcoming the limitation of traditional teaching-playing. Vision sensor have great measurement efficiency, lower cost and moderate accuracy, so it has been increasingly used for pose estimation. Generally, only one camera is not enough to estimate 3D pose, hence it is usually combined with other equipment, such as laser finder, inertia sensor or just another cameras. Laser finder has great measurement range and precision, while there high price make it impractical for most industrial robot¹. And inertia sensor is relatively economical, but the low frequency noise would lead to large error, complicated optimization algorithm must be introduced to improve the accuracy². However, vision system composed of camera, image processing technique and specific algorithm can estimating pose efficiently, and it can be employed in building fast and accurate aid-positioning system for robot.

Most studies on 3D pose estimation focus on the problem of estimating the pose of targets in space using stereo vision³⁻⁵. Zhang *et al*³. introduced a binocular vision system for the pose estimation for Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV), after feature points are detected with the Harris algorithm, the NCC algorithm is conducted to complete feature matching, finally with the 3D feature points, the position and attitude can be computed with RANSAC algorithm and L-M iteration algorithm. Frosio *et al*⁴. proposed to estimate the position and orientation of a plane by three projection of a conic lying on the plane, the non-linear terms was eliminated by combining the three projection equation, and the parameter of the plane can be computed by solving the obtained linear equation. Udaya and Park *et al*⁵. proposed a binocular vision system for bin picking, they extracts the label areas by various of image processing, then they features in these areas are matched to generate 3D label surface. Their matching process includes two steps, the initial matching is based on brute-force algorithm, and then the epipolar geometry⁶ based on outlier removing technique is applied to increase the robustness of the feature matching. When two or more cameras are used, a priori knowledge about the target is not necessary, but these systems associated to the problem of time consuming because of the stereo matching. Besides, the available workspace of stereo vision is the intersection region of all cameras, which imposes restriction on the application of stereo vision.

To overcome the shortcomings of above-mentioned stereo vision, recent years, some researchers present that cooperative targets can be designed for estimating 3D pose by monocular vision, with the additional constraints conditions, like the shape or the size of targets, the pose of the cooperative targets can be estimated only by single projection. In[7], the cooperative target is 4 spatial points who can form a parallelogram, the mapping model of the rigid body pose and 2D image is constructed based on the two vanished points of the parallelogram geometric constraint, and with the mapping model,

the 3d pose of the rigid body can be estimated according to its coordinates in 2D image. And Han⁸ presents a method for estimating pose by the single projection of the door-type frame, after extracting the three lines by image processing, the intersection points and the vanished points of the two parallel lines can be obtained, further, the relative pose between the camera frame and reference frame can be modeled with the vanished point theory and vertical conditions of lines. Similarly, Zhu *et al*⁹. adopt 3 spatial lines which are perpendicular to each other and intersect at 2 points to estimate the relative pose between camera and object, they analyzes the vertical relationship among lines and normal vectors of planes to find out the closed-form solution of the problem.

Circle is one of the most fundamental feature in computer vision, they are frequently adopted as reliable markers for calibration and for tracking objects in 3D space. Compared with points and lines who lead to simpler mathematical formulation, circles contains more geometrical constraint and the projection of a circle is an ellipse which is easy to model. Because of these reasons, a wide range of applications based on circle have been described in literature, including camera calibration¹⁰, guiding of robot¹¹ and so on. Camera calibration method based on concentric circle is proposed by Zhang¹⁰, it described how to estimate the projection of the circle center by formulating the problem into a first order polynomial eigenvalue problem, and how the camera can be calibrated with the images of circular points or vanishing points. Li¹¹ proposes a monocular vision system which can recognizing colored ball rapidly for guiding of home security robot, the ball is detected by checking if the radius is within the given range after object segment based on color feature.

In this paper, we present a monocular vision based 3D pose estimation algorithm, which can compute the 3D pose of the target by single image, and the methods relies on the circle target with the radius known. Projecting the circle target into an upright ellipse cone and analyzing the geometrical

relationship in the cone we derive part of the depth information of several extreme points. By the 3D position of these extreme points we further determine the pose of the circle in 3D space. The cooperative target used in this method is circle, circle is common and easy to fabricate in the industrial environment, which makes the method available for a wide range of application, like the automatic drilling and components assembly. Only one image is needed for 3D pose estimation, with the time-consuming stereo matching process avoided, the algorithm is more real-time. Besides, the whole mathematic model is based on the extreme geometry of the perspective projection model, non-iteration makes it more concise and easy to program the algorithm.

This paper is organized as follows. In Section 1 the related work is presented in the introduction. Section 2 describes the involved frames and the basic models. Section 3 gives details of the pose estimation algorithm. The experimental results are presented in Section 4 while the conclusion is given in Section 5

2 Frames and Basic model

The geometrical relationship mentioned in this paper is based on the pin-hole camera imaging model, it involves 3 main frames: pixel coordinate system, camera coordinate system, and reference coordinate system. The 2D pixel coordinate system $o-uv$ is established in pixels on the top left corner of the image directly, in addition, there is a physical image coordinate system $o'-xy$ which is superposed with the pixel plane, and the origin point o' is in the center of the pixel plane, coordinates in the two systems can be transformed into each other with the following Eq. (1):

$$\begin{cases} u = x/dx + u_0 \\ v = y/dy + v_0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

(u, v) is pixel coordinate, (x, y) is the physical image coordinate, dx is the width of CCD or CMOS imaging unit in the x axis direction, and dy is in the y in the same way, (u_0, v_0) is the origin point offset of the two coordinate systems.

The camera perspective projection geometry is shown in Fig.1. The origin point of camera coordinate system $O-X_c Y_c Z_c$ is the camera optical center, and the $X_c O Y_c$ plane is parallel to the plane uov , and the Z_c axis is the optical axis. The reference coordinate system $O_w - X_w Y_w Z_w$ is introduced to describe the pose of the camera in the space.

Fig. 1 The camera perspective projection geometry

The relationship between pixel coordinate system and camera coordinate is called intrinsic parameter, and the relationship between camera coordinate system and world coordinate system is extrinsic parameter, they can be described as:

$$z_c \begin{bmatrix} u \\ v \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} f/dx & 0 & u_0 \\ 0 & f/dy & v_0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_c \\ y_c \\ z_c \end{bmatrix}, \quad (2)$$

$$X_c = [\mathbf{R} \quad \mathbf{t}] X_w, \quad (3)$$

f is the focal length, (x_c, y_c, z_c) is the camera coordinates. It's worth noting that in order to improve the precision of vision measurement, the lens distortion¹² must be taken into consideration. The extrinsic parameter includes the rotation matrix \mathbf{R} and translation vector \mathbf{t} between the world coordinates $O_w - X_w Y_w Z_w$ and camera coordinates $O - X_c Y_c Z_c$. Camera calibration must be executed to obtain the value of intrinsic and extrinsic parameters.

To implement the method, firstly the camera takes photo of the circle target in any pose, and the circle will show as an ellipse in the image since the image plane is not parallel with the target plane, the projecting relationship can be described as Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 The imaging model in camera coordinate system

In order to get circle information, the image must be processed to make it easier to extract feature points which make up the circle target contour with noise reduction, binarization, and edge detection and so on. These contour points can be described as (u_i, v_i) , n is the number of the extracted feature points, and $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$.

3 Position estimation algorithm

Here we show how to estimate the 3D pose of the circle with the image coordinates of its circumferential contour. The contour of circle appears to be an ellipse in the image, and it can form an oblique elliptic cone with the optical center O . Imaginably, the generatrices of the oblique elliptic cone are in the direction of projecting rays, and there must be an upright elliptic cone shares the same generatrices with the oblique elliptic under the condition of giving the height.

Firstly, the centerline of the upright elliptic cone has been calculated. On account that single camera loses the depth of feature points, what we can get are the directions of projecting rays merely. The homogeneous camera coordinates $(x_i, y_i, 1)$ of these points can be computed with the internal parameter. By setting the value of z_{ci} , all the projecting rays can be adjusted to the equal length of α_0 with the following formula:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{x_{ci}}{x_i} = \frac{y_{ci}}{y_i} = z_{ci} \\ x_{ci}^2 + y_{ci}^2 + z_{ci}^2 = \alpha_0^2 \end{cases}, \quad (4)$$

α_0 can be any number except zero, and (x_{ci}, y_{ci}, z_{ci}) is the camera coordinates for contour points after above transformation. The geometric average value O_0 of these points should be the center of the sub face ellipse of one upright elliptic cone, and the line OO_0 should be the center line, the computation process is as following:

$$\begin{aligned} X_i^c &= \sqrt{\alpha_0^2 / (x_i^2 + y_i^2 + 1)} \times [x_i \quad y_i \quad 1]^T, \\ &= [x_{ci} \quad y_{ci} \quad z_{ci}]^T \end{aligned}, \quad (5)$$

$$X_o = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n X_i^c}{n} = [\bar{x}_c \quad \bar{y}_c \quad \bar{z}_c]^T, \quad (6)$$

However, to get the geometric average value O_0 , generatrices corresponding to these contour points must be distributed uniformly as Fig. 3 shown. The contour is uneven because of the illumination (Fig. 4), before adjusting the length of projecting rays, we must sample hundreds of

contour points satisfying the above-mentioned uniform distribution, ε_0 is the included angle of the adjacent generatrices. We first fit the general equation of the oblique ellipse (Eq. (7)) in the 2D physical image plane with points (x_i, y_i) by the Ellipse Direct Fit method¹³. Secondly, transforming it to standard equation (Eq. (11)) and polar equation (Eq.12) according to Eq. (7) ~ (12). Thirdly, we can obtain hundreds of points by sampling the ellipse circumference every 0.1° of ε_0 according to Eq. (13, 14), where m is the number of selected points whose rotation angle is θ_j .

$$F(x, y) = ax^2 + bxy + cy^2 + dx + ey + f = 0, \quad (7)$$

$$\begin{cases} aX^2 + bXY + cY^2 + F = 0 \\ X = x - x_0 \\ Y = y - y_0 \end{cases}, \quad (8)$$

$$\begin{cases} x_0 = \frac{2cd - be}{b^2 - 4ac} \\ y_0 = \frac{2ae - bd}{b^2 - 4ac} \end{cases}, \quad (9)$$

$$\begin{cases} p = X \cos \alpha + Y \sin \alpha \\ q = -X \sin \alpha + Y \cos \alpha \omega, \\ \tan 2\omega = \frac{b}{a - c} \end{cases}, \quad (10)$$

$$\begin{cases} \frac{p^2}{\sigma^2} + \frac{q^2}{\tau^2} = 1 \\ \sigma = \sqrt{\frac{c \cos \omega^2 - a \sin \omega^2}{\cos 2\omega}}, \\ \tau = \sqrt{\frac{a \cos \omega^2 - c \sin \omega^2}{\cos 2\omega}} \end{cases}, \quad (11)$$

$$\begin{cases} p = \sigma \cos \theta \\ q = \tau \sin \theta \end{cases}, \quad (12)$$

$$\begin{cases} x_j = \sigma \cos \theta_j \cos \omega - \tau \sin \theta_j \sin \omega + x_0 \\ y_j = \sigma \cos \theta_j \sin \omega + \tau \sin \theta_j \cos \omega + y_0 \end{cases} \quad (j = 1, 3, 4 \dots m), \quad (13)$$

$$\begin{cases} \cos(\varepsilon_0) = (L_{j-1}^2 - 2(l_{j-1}^2 - l_{j-1} \cos(\theta_j - \theta_{j-1})) / L_{j-1} \\ l_{j-1} = \sqrt{x_{j-1}^2 + y_{j-1}^2} \\ L_{j-1} = \sqrt{x_{j-1}^2 + y_{j-1}^2 + 1} \end{cases} \begin{cases} \theta_1 = 0 \\ \theta_m \rightarrow 360^\circ \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

Fig. 3 The thickness of the contour is uneven

Fig. 4 The selected generatrices must be distributed uniformly

Secondly, the sub face ellipse of the upright elliptic cone has been computed. Rotating the Z_c axis of the camera coordinates system to OO_0 , a new camera coordinate system $O-X_c'Y_c'Z_c'$ has been built. Then, it can translate the homogeneous coordinates $(x_i, y_i, 1)$ to $O-X_c'Y_c'Z_c'$ system according to the Eq. (15) ~ (18):

$$\begin{cases} \eta = a \tan 2(\bar{y}_c, \bar{z}_c) \\ \rho = a \tan 2(\bar{x}_c, \bar{y}_c \sin \alpha + \bar{z}_c \cos \alpha) \end{cases}, \quad (15)$$

$$R_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos \eta & -\sin \eta \\ 0 & \sin \eta & \cos \eta \end{bmatrix}, \quad (16)$$

$$R_2 = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \rho & 0 & -\sin \rho \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ \sin \rho & 0 & \cos \rho \end{bmatrix},$$

$$R = R_2 R_1, \quad (17)$$

$$X_{ci} = R[x_i \quad y_i \quad 1]', \quad (18)$$

Where \mathbf{R} is the rotation matrix of the two cameras coordinate systems. Then adjust all values of X_{ci3} to the constant χ_0 according to Eq. (19) with the direction of OX_{ci} unaltered. X_{ci}' is the contour point after the translation and the optimal value of χ_0 should be 2 to 5 times of the object distance.

$$X_{ci}' = \frac{X_{ci}}{X_{ci3}} \chi_0 = [x_{ci}' \quad y_{ci}' \quad z_{ci}'], \quad (19)$$

All of the X_{ci}' are in the new image plane P_1' , the ellipse they compose can form an upright elliptic cone with the optical point. Also, the ellipse fitting is again completed according to Eq. (7~12). The σ is the major axis radius and τ is the minor axis radius, and the (x_0, y_0) is the center offset of the ellipse, α is the tilt angle of the ellipse.

After we obtain the mathematic model of the upright ellipse cone through above steps, according to the Fig. 5, the distance between the optical point O and points A, B, C and D can be computed with the geometric relationship. In the upright ellipse cone, the plane passed optical point O and major axis is called plane-C, and the plane passed optical point O and minor axis is called plane-A. O_1 is the midpoint of the interaction line of circle target plane and plane-C. r is the radius of the circle target, and a is the distance between O_1 and O_2 . A and B is the two contact points of the two generatrices in plane-A and circumference as shown Fig. 4, C and D is the two contact points of the two generatrices in plane-C and circumference. Indicating with $\angle OAB = \gamma$, α is the base angle of the isosceles triangle in plane-C and β is the base angle of the isosceles triangle in plane-A and they can be computed with Eq. (20):

$$\begin{cases} \alpha = \frac{\pi}{2} - \arctan \frac{\sigma}{\chi_0} \\ \beta = \frac{\pi}{2} - \arctan \frac{\tau}{\chi_0} \end{cases}, \quad (20)$$

The lengths of OO_1 and OC can be computed with Eq. (21) according to the geometric relation in target circle and plane-C.

$$\begin{cases} |O_1C| = \sqrt{r^2 - a^2} \\ |OC| = |OD| = \sqrt{r^2 - a^2} / \cos \alpha \end{cases}, \quad (21)$$

Fig. 5 Geometric relation of the projecting imaging and extreme points.

Fig. 6 Geometric relations in plane-A.

The geometric relation in plane-A can be concluded as Fig. 6. Using the Sine Law in triangle OBO_1 and triangle OO_1A , we can get Eq. (22):

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\cos \beta}{r+a} = \frac{\sin \gamma}{\sqrt{r^2 - a^2} \tan \alpha} \\ \frac{\cos \beta}{r-a} = \frac{\sin(2\beta - \gamma)}{\sqrt{r^2 - a^2} \tan \alpha} \end{cases}, \quad (22)$$

Solving Eq. (22), the value of the auxiliary variable γ can be calculated. Further, utilizing the Sine Law in the triangle OAB we can get the value of $|OA|$ and $|OB|$:

$$|OA| = \frac{2r \times \sin(2\beta - \gamma)}{\sin(\pi - 2\beta)}, \quad (23)$$

$$|OB| = \frac{2r \times \sin \gamma}{\sin(\pi - 2\beta)}, \quad (24)$$

According to the ellipse fitting, in the new camera coordinate system, the coordinates of the 2 major axis vertexes are X_1 and X_2 , and the minor axis vertexes are Y_1 and Y_2 , and they can be transformed into the real camera system by Eq. (25-27):

$$\begin{cases} X_1 = [\sigma \times \cos \alpha, \sigma \times \sin \alpha, 0]' + [x_0, y_0, \chi_0]' \\ X_2 = [-\sigma \times \cos \alpha, -\sigma \times \sin \alpha, 0]' + [x_0, y_0, \chi_0]' \\ Y_1 = [-\tau \times \sin \alpha, \tau \times \cos \alpha, 0]' + [x_0, y_0, \chi_0]' \\ Y_2 = [\tau \times \sin \alpha, -\tau \times \cos \alpha, 0]' + [x_0, y_0, \chi_0]' \end{cases}, \quad (25)$$

$$X_{c_k} = \begin{bmatrix} Lx_k \\ Ly_k \\ Lz_k \end{bmatrix} = R^{-1} X_k \quad (k=1,2), \quad (26)$$

$$Y_{c_k} = \begin{bmatrix} Sx_k \\ Sy_k \\ Sz_k \end{bmatrix} = R^{-1} Y_k \quad (k=1,2), \quad (27)$$

Where X_{c_k} and Y_{c_k} are the coordinates of the four vertexes in real camera system. Obviously, X_{c1} and X_{c2} are the direction vectors of OA and OB , and Y_{c1} , Y_{c2} are the direction vectors of OC and OD respectively. At this point, we acquire the direction vectors and depth information of the 4 extreme geometric points, so the 3D camera coordinates of the circumference points A, B, C, D can be computed by:

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_c \\ y_c \\ z_c \end{bmatrix} = \frac{|OC|}{|Y_{c1}|} Y_{c1}, \quad (28)$$

and the 3D coordinates of another three circumference points can be computed with the similar relationship. Finally, the circle target can be fitted with the four circumference points, and the center of the circle is the position while then norm vector of the plane the circle lies on is the orientation.

However, when computing the coordinate of A and B , the corresponding relation between X_{c1} , X_{c2} and OA , OB is uncertain, in another word, the proposed algorithm is ambiguous so far. Actually, when solving Eq. (22), there always exist 2 solutions of the equation, one is acute angle and another is obtuse angle, except when the upright elliptic cone we obtain is upright cone. As the Fig. 7 shown, when we adopt different γ , the value of $|OA|$ and $|OB|$ will exchange with each other. Therefore, other constraint is needed to eliminate the wrong solution in practice.

Fig. 7 The ambiguity: 2 γ lead to 2 solutions.

4 Experiment and Results

4.1 Simulation Test

To validate the proposed algorithm, we used it to estimate poses of circles, and evaluated its performance by comparing with the methods proposed by Frosio³, Udaya⁵ and Han⁸. As shown in Fig. 8, a CMOS camera with 1280×1024 pixels and 75 bps was used. The camera was calibrated through Zhang's method implemented in Matlab¹³. To this aim, 25 images of a checkerboard, with a random pose in 3D space, were acquired. The standard deviation of the projection error never exceeded 0.09 pixels, with a maximum error of 0.45 pixels.

Fig. 8 The camera installed upside down on the tripod is acquiring the image of circles.

The 3d pose can be described by 6 parameters as Eq. (29), the First 3 parameters are the coordinate in the camera system, and the last 3 parameters, the normal vector of the circle plane, indicate the orientation. Generally, a high precision measurement system should be applied to positioning the circle with sufficiently higher accuracy and obtain the true poses of circles in the camera system, but the solution would be costly. Therefore, we measured 2 standard circles, lying on a plane, whose true distance is 40mm and orientations are identical, and replaces the absolute pose error by the relative pose error.

$$P = (p_1, p_2, p_3, r_1, r_2, r_3), \quad (29)$$

The relative pose accuracy is composed of position error E_p and orientation error E_r defined by Eq. (30), P_a and P_b are the measured poses of the 2 circles, and E_p is measured distance between them, while E_r is their included angle.

$$\begin{cases} E_p = \sqrt{(p_{1a} - p_{1b})^2 + (p_{2a} - p_{2b})^2 + (p_{3a} - p_{3b})^2} - 40 \\ E_r = a \cos \left(\frac{r_{1a}r_{1b} + r_{2a}r_{2b} + r_{3a}r_{3b}}{\sqrt{r_{1a}^2 + r_{2a}^2 + r_{3a}^2} \times \sqrt{r_{1b}^2 + r_{2b}^2 + r_{3b}^2}} \right) \end{cases}, \quad (30)$$

To analyze the accuracy of the method in the whole workspace, we acquired images of the 2 circles in different distances and different orientations. Firstly, the lens was focused manually at the distance of 350mm , then, as shown in Fig. 9, the marker was put at the height of about 300mm , 350mm and 400mm , and the place angle varied from -45° to 45° in 3 locations of each height, finally a total of 171 images can be captured with every 5° a shoot. The position error and orientation error are reported graphically as a function of tilt angle in Fig. 10.

Fig. 9 The approximate position and tile angle where the flat plate located when images were captured.

Fig. 10 The pose error as a function of tilt angle.

The error line chart of the 9 sets of pose are arranged consistently with their placing location. The median of position/orientation error is $0.2351\text{mm}/0.6065^\circ$, and the average of position/orientation error is $0.3797\text{mm}/0.7846^\circ$, while the maximum of position/orientation error is $1.7479\text{mm}/2.4915^\circ$. Two phenomena can be concluded through Fig. 11. Firstly, there exists an obvious peak of angle error, and the peaks locate in the same tilt angle in each column and move to right in each row. We noticed, the peak would appear when the circle plane inclines to perpendicular to the centerline of the mentioned upright ellipse cone. Therefore, we should avoid the singular location when employing the proposed method in estimating orientation directly. By removing the angle errors of singular locations, the median/average/maximum of angle error is $0.5381^\circ/0.6711^\circ/1.8029^\circ$. Secondly, the position error

whose median is 0.2351 is comparatively small, and it attains to valley when the tilt angle closes to zero. But when the tilt angle becomes large, the position error ascends in the first and second column, while the situation doesn't appear in the third column. We found the illumination ceiling lamp bias toward right, the measured circle were in the shadow when the tilt angle was large in the left zone.

We compared the accuracy of the proposed method with Frosio⁴, Udaya⁵ and Han⁸'s methods. The method of Frosio⁴ and Udaya⁵ are based on stereo vision, and Han used only one camera too, while his cooperative target is door-type frame. The medians, average or maximum of their pose error are reported numerically in Table 1.

Table 1 Median or Average of the pose error of 4 method

	Proposed method		Frosio's method		Udaya's method		Han's method	
	Monocular vision		Trinocular vision		Binocular vision		Monocular vision	
	Dist (mm)	Angle (°)	Dist (mm)	Angle (°)	Dist (mm)	Angle (°)	Dist (mm)	Angle (°)
Median	0.2351	0.5381	0.01	0.06	-	-	-	-
Average	0.3797	0.6711	-	-	0.748	-	-	-
Max	1.7479	1.8029	-	-	-	-	2.8	1.2

Comparing to stereo vision, no matter position error or orientation error, the proposed method is less accurate according to the median of their pose error, especially for Frosio's trinocular vision based on conic target. Udaya didn't provide orientation error, while the proposed monocular vision has better position accuracy than the binocular vision proposed by Udaya according to their average position error. When only one camera is used, the proposed method achieves an obviously higher position accuracy with respect to Han's method according to their maximal position error, while our orientation

accuracy is slightly lower than Han's method. The max pose error in table 1 is an approximated value for Han only provides the error curve but not numerical error.

Therefore, when both stereo vision and cooperative target are used, the method would be more accurate than method with only one of them is adopted. While comparing to binocular vision, the proposed monocular vision with cooperative target has much better position accuracy. However, the monocular vision is more concise for only one projection is needed, while the feature matching must be conducted to construct the mapping between images. Besides, the global calibration and intersection of workspaces between cameras make the stereo vision less efficient than monocular vision. When only one camera is used, our method based on circle feature is more accurate in position and slightly less accurate in orientation than the method based on line features. But the target for Han's method must be a door-type frame which is quite not common in industrial environment, while arbitrary circles, like location holes and round head screw can be used to estimate the 3D pose with the proposed method.

4.2 Application Case

We have validated the efficiency and analyzed the accuracy of the proposed method, further we applied the method to the aid-positioning of a parallel robot¹⁵ as Fig. 11(a) shown. The camera was installed on the moving platform of the parallel robot, the reference system is the robot coordinate system, and calibration had been done to get the intrinsic and extrinsic parameter. For the parallel robot is 3-DOF, we just observed the position measurement. As shown Fig. 11(b), the precisely-machined marker is a disc with lots of small standard circular cylinders whose radius is *6mm*.

Fig. 11(a) The camera installed on the moving platform of the parallel robot is capturing images of circle cylinders;

Fig. 11(b) The standard marker with lots of circle cylinders.

In the experiment, the position estimated by the vision sensor guided the end-effector to the circular cylinders, and then a displacement sensor installed on the moving platform would be used to measure the position error. While the camera and the displacement sensor can't be installed on the moving platform at the same time, so we divided the experiment to 2 steps. Firstly, We only installed the camera, and moved the moving platform of the robot closely to the circular cylinders to acquired hundreds of images, after computing the position of these circular cylinders, we stored them in a readable file. Secondly, we dismantled the camera and installed the displacement sensor, and robot was guided to these desired positions by the data stored in the file successively, and the distances between the end-effector and the circular cylinders would be measured by the displacement sensor as shown in Fig. 12. The resolution of the used displacement sensor is 0.01mm . Finally, 365 position errors were collected, and they are reported graphically in Fig. 13.

According to the curve in Fig. 13, 5 circle cylinders in one image have similar error value, while the distance error varies in different capturing place. The diversity of shooting location and natural

illumination should be responsible for the phenomenon. The median/average/maximum distance error is $0.69\text{mm}/0.77\text{mm}/1.68\text{mm}$, which is quite moderate for the position estimation for robot.

Fig. 12 The displacement sensor was installed on the moving platform to measure the distance error

Fig. 13 The distance error distribution of 365 data.

5 Conclusion and Further Work

In this paper, we proposed an algorithm for estimating the pose of a circle in space, based on only one projection of single camera. Transforming the original oblique cone geometry of circle projection, which is difficult to model, to an upright ellipse cone, then resorting the known radius and several extreme space points to recover part depth information of the circle, and finally obtaining its 3d pose. Experimental concern the measurement accuracy shows the algorithm is efficient to estimate the 3D pose of circle objects, the max position error is less than $1.75mm$, and the max orientation error is 2° .

The experiment result and the data analysis shows the accuracy is not enough for high-precision measurement actually, and the center line mentioned in Section. 3 is a key factor for improving the accuracy. While when we sampled the contour points for computing the centerline, the length of l_j and L_j of the j th point are approximate to l_{j-1} and L_{j-1} , the explicit mathematic mapping between include angle of adjacent generatrices and contour points should be modeled. And the singular location for capturing images affect the orientation accuracy so much, specific coping strategy should be proposed to avoid it or solve it. In addition, the proposed method is ambiguous by only one circle without any other constraints, the method for eliminating the wrong solution need to be developed to make the method available for more objects.

Acknowledgements

This work is supported by National Natural Science Foundation of China (51420105007 and 51475320), the Key Technologies R & D Program of Tianjin (15ZXZNGX00220), and EU H2020 project (734272).

References

1. Zhao R. 3D location of non-cooperative circle target based on monocular vision and laser range finder[C]// International Conference on Automatic Control and Artificial Intelligence. IET, 2013:1- 4.
2. Duc T M, Kang H J. Fusion of Vision and Inertial Sensors for Position-Based Visual Servoing of a Robot Manipulator[M]// Intelligent Computing Theories. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2013:536-545.
3. Zhang L, Xu J, Xia Q. Pose estimation algorithm and verification based on binocular stereo vision for unmanned aerial vehicle[J]. Journal of Harbin Institute of Technology, 2014, 46(5):66-72.
4. Frosio I, Alzati A, Bertolini M, et al. Linear pose estimate from corresponding conics[J]. Pattern Recognition, 2012, 45(12):4169-4181.
5. Wijenayake U, Choi S I, Park S Y. Stereo Vision-Based 3D Pose Estimation of Product Labels for Bin Picking[J]. Acta Obstetricia Et Gynecologica Scandinavica, 2016, 22(4):369-380.
6. Li C, Zhao Y. Approach of Camera Relative Pose Estimation Based on Epipolar Geometry[J]. Information Technology Journal, 2012, 11(9):1202-1210.
7. Ding Y, Mei J, Zhang W, et al. Position and Orientation Measurement of Parallel Robot Based on Monocular Vision[J]. Journal of Mechanical Engineering, 2014, 50(21):174.
8. Han L, Wang X, Huang C, et al. Door-shaped Structure Based Monocular Vision Locating Method[J]. Optoelectronic Technology, 2014, 34(2).
9. Chang L, Feng Z, Jin-Jun O U. Monocular Pose Determination from Three Perpendicular Lines[J]. Pattern Recognition & Artificial Intelligence, 2012, 25(5):737-744.
10. Eberli D et al., “Vision Based Position Control for MAVs Using One Single Circular Landmark,” *J. Intell. Robot. Syst.* **61**(1), 495-512 (2011) [[doi: 10.1049/iet-ipr.2011.0421](https://doi.org/10.1049/iet-ipr.2011.0421)].

11. Li S A et al., “Circle object recognition based on monocular vision for home security robot,” in *International Symposium on Intelligent Signal Processing and Communications Systems*, 258-261(2013) [doi: [10.1109/ISPACS.2012.6473491](https://doi.org/10.1109/ISPACS.2012.6473491)].
12. Ricolfe-Viala C, Sánchez-Salmerón A J. Correcting non-linear lens distortion in cameras without using a model[J]. *Optics & Laser Technology*, 2010, 42(4):628-639.
13. Fitzgibbon A, Pilu M, and Fisher R B. “Direct least square fitting of ellipses,” *IEEE Trans. Patt. Anal. Mach. Int.* **21**(5), 476-480 (1999) [doi:[10.1109/34.765658](https://doi.org/10.1109/34.765658)].
14. Lu P, Liu Q, and Guo J. “Camera Calibration Implementation Based on Zhang Zhengyou Plane Method,” in *Proceedings of the 2015 Chinese Intelligent Systems Conference* (2016) [doi: [10.1007/978-3-662-48386-2_4](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-662-48386-2_4)].
15. Mei J, Ni Y, Li Y, et al. The error modeling and accuracy synthesis of a 3-DOF parallel robot Delta-S[C]// *International Conference on Information and Automation*. IEEE, 2009:289-294.[doi: [10.1109/ICINFA.2009.5204937](https://doi.org/10.1109/ICINFA.2009.5204937)]

Jiangping Mei is an associate professor and a PhD candidate supervisor at the Tianjin University. He received his MS and PhD degree in Machine Design, Manufacturing and Automation from the School of Mechanical Engineering from Tianjin University 1995 and 2005, respectively. He has published 25 papers in journals cited by SCI/EI, and authorized 21 patents at home, and developed 2 to 4 DOF high-speed parallel robot. His research interests include manufacturing system and industrial robot.

Yabin Ding serves as the associate professor at Tianjin University. Prior to joining Tianjin University in 2007 he graduated with a Ph.D. degree in Measuring Technology and Instrument from School of Precision Instrument and Opto-Electronics Engineering. He has published 21 papers in journals cited

by SCI/EI, and authorized over 4 patents at home, and participated in 3 national research projects of China. Currently, Ding's academic interests are in optical metrology technologies for aircraft structure manufacturing.

Dian Zhang is a graduate student at Tianjin University. She received her BS degree in Mechanical Engineering from Tianjin University in 2015. Her current research includes vision-aided positioning technology for robots.

Caption List

Fig. 1 The camera perspective projection geometry.

Fig. 2 The imaging model in camera coordinate system.

Fig. 3 The thickness of the contour is uneven.

Fig. 4 The selected generatrices must be distributed uniformly.

Fig. 5 Geometric relation of the projecting imaging and extreme points.

Fig. 6 Geometric relations in plane- A .

Fig. 7 The ambiguity: $2 \quad \gamma$ lead to 2 solutions.

Fig. 8 The camera installed upside down on the tripod is acquiring the image of circles.

Fig. 9 The approximate position and tilt angle where the flat plate located when images were captured.

Fig. 10 The pose error as a function of tilt angle.

Fig. 11(a) The camera installed on the moving platform of the parallel robot is capturing images of circle cylinders;

Fig. 11(b) The standard marker with lots of circle cylinders.

Fig. 12 The displacement sensor was installed on the moving platform to measure the distance error.

Fig. 13 The distance error distribution of 365 data.